

THE CONTENT OF FORMING SOCIAL SKILLS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS.

Asian International University 1nd stage graduate student:

Madaminov Muhammad Yusuf

Abstract: We know that the formation of social skills among schoolchildren in our country is one of the most urgent problems. In this thesis, we talk about the content of forming social skills in elementary school students.

Key words: Social skills, Social adaptation, Socialization, Individualization, rules of behavior, moral resources.

Main part: Social skills are acquired elements of social behavior, which are related to the knowledge of the social world, self and its place in this bright world, behaviors that facilitate social interactions, and the person. It is based on actions that enable effective establishment of relationships with the environment, determination of one's place and expression of identity, and this contributes to successful social adaptation and socialization in general. Socialization is determined by the development and change of a person in the process of acquiring culture. We know that this phenomenon is studied in the field of social pedagogy. This is the difference between social pedagogy and the field of pedagogy. The subject of pedagogy is the laws of raising a child, and the subject of social pedagogy is the laws of child socialization. The life of a person lives directly in society, among the people who live in it. The effective course of interpersonal relations between members of society directly depends on the content of social relations of a person. The content of social relations, in turn, is determined by the determination of social norms, the degree to which they are recognized by society, and the extent to which they are observed in practical activities. In the process of education, the person directly interacts with the social and cultural environment, and it has an educational effect on the person. Social norms are the basis of interpersonal relations and are formed according to the characteristics reflected in them. Although this is so, the essence of social norms is not always understood by the members of the society. According to observations, the essence of social norms in many cases can be understood to a certain extent only by persons who have special knowledge in the legal field, namely, those who work in the judicial, tax, customs or internal affairs systems. Therefore, on the basis of the

cluster approach, it is even more important that everyone should be aware of social norms and their content.

Pupils studying in primary grades acquire the first basic concepts of social norms and their content in the family and preschool educational institutions. However, the stage of primary education is a special period in the life of students. The child will be fully ready for education according to his physical and mental maturity. The main activity of life is replaced by the activity of reading. Study activity has a strong influence on the mental development of students and the formation of character traits. Interest in learning and studying the environment increases. All of these events help students to understand the essence of social norms. An emotional approach to knowledge is manifested as one of the characteristics of primary school students. Therefore, when introducing them to social norms, the information provided in an interesting way, figurative interpretation with the help of life examples as much as possible, helps to achieve positive results. Due to their tendency to express their feelings, and at the same time, the strength of imitating their peers, the situations of following social and moral norms or not following them, by highlighting the examples of their behavior, behavior, and habits, are enough for their imagination. there is a possibility to achieve.

Conclusion: The content of forming social skills in elementary school students is one of the important parts of the general educational process. This content provides students with information on how to behave in interpersonal relationships, the structure of society and communication with other people. The process of forming social skills is carried out by teaching students through manuals, problems and examples. In this content, students are shown in a broad way topics such as mutual respect, helping friends, fulfilling one's duty in the future, and being a useful member of society.

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